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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

(A Double Blind Peer-reviewed International Journal)

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Assessing the Impact of Khadi and Village Industries on Employment and Economic Sustainability: A Pathway to Social Development

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ABSTRACT

Khadi and Village Industries (KVI) has long been a foundational element of India's rural economy, contributing to employment, economic sustainability, and social development. This study adopts a quantitative approach, utilizing secondary data derived from the Annual Reports of MSMEs and KVIC. The analysis employs correlation and regression techniques, alongside the Durbin-Watson test and ANOVA, to evaluate the impact of KVI on economic and social sustainability.

The findings reveal a correlation coefficient of 0.997, indicating a highly positive association between production and employment in the KVI sector. The p-value of 0.000, significant at the 0.01 level, highlights the robustness of this relationship. The regression model demonstrates that production is a key determinant of employment, explaining 99.5% of the variance in employment outcomes. This substantial explanatory power underscores the importance of production in shaping employment trends within the sector. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.922 further affirms the model's reliability by confirming the absence of significant autocorrelation in the residuals, enhancing the credibility of the results.

The regression equation suggests that for every increase of 1 lakh rupees in production, employment rises by 0.000008 lakh persons, with a t-statistic of 31.540 (p-value 0.000), confirming the statistical significance of production. The residual statistics show that predicted employment values range from 135.68 lakh to 176.47 lakh persons, with a mean of 154.32 lakh persons and a standard deviation of 1.037, reflecting the high accuracy of the model's forecasts. Overall, the analysis supports the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis, confirming a significant relationship between production and employment in the KVI sector.

Keywords: Khadi and Village Industries, Economic Sustainability, Social Development Employment, Rural Empowerment

INTRODUCTION

The Khadi and Village Industries Commission (KVIC), established in 1957 under the ministry of micro, small & medium enterprises, stands as a foundational institution in India's rural economic development. Dedicated to promoting and nurturing KVI sector, KVIC has played a pivotal role in fostering economic sustainability, preserving traditional crafts, and empowering rural communities. Through its various initiatives, KVIC has significantly contributed to improving livelihoods, reducing rural poverty, and promoting social and economic resilience across the country.

The guiding principles of KVIC are deeply rooted in the vision of Mahatma Gandhi, who regarded Khadi not merely as a fabric, but as a movement towards self-reliance and rural empowerment. Gandhi viewed Khadi as a vehicle for socio-economic transformation, a means to decentralize production, and an instrument for fostering equitable economic opportunities. His belief that "the spinning wheel represents to me the hope of the masses" captured the essence of Khadi's potential to uplift rural communities, instill dignity, and generate pride among artisans. Gandhi's vision, emphasizing local production, equitable resource distribution, and sustainable living, continues to resonate with contemporary global

frameworks of sustainable development. KVIC's initiatives align with the United Nations (UNs) SDGs, addressing key global challenges such as poverty, gender inequality, and environmental sustainability. KVIC's work directly addresses the eradication of poverty by creating employment opportunities for marginalized communities, particularly in rural areas. By providing skill development programs, facilitating financial access, and expanding market reach for artisans, KVIC enhances economic stability in these underserved regions, thereby contributing to national economic growth and poverty alleviation.

In addition to poverty reduction, KVIC's initiatives support gender equality by empowering women in the rural workforce. Through its various schemes, KVIC has provided women artisans with opportunities for entrepreneurship, leadership, and active participation in local economies. By promoting women's economic independence, KVIC plays a crucial role in advancing gender inclusivity and fostering a more equitable socio-economic structure.

KVIC's promotion of sustainable production methods further demonstrates its commitment to environmental conservation. Khadi, with its eco-friendly production processes, embodies the principles of responsible consumption and production, key tenets of global sustainable development. By advocating for Khadi as a green and ethical alternative to mass-produced textiles, KVIC not only supports the reduction of environmental degradation but also caters to the growing global demand for sustainable and ethically manufactured products. KVIC's focus on decentralized production systems fosters the creation of decent work and sustainable economic growth. By generating millions of jobs in rural areas and ensuring fair wages, KVIC reduces migration to urban centers, stimulates regional development, and bolsters the economic resilience of rural communities. Its decentralized model enhances social stability, contributing to a more balanced distribution of economic opportunities across the country.

This paper seeks to offer a thorough analysis of KVIC's contributions to India's socio-economic development. By examining its role in poverty alleviation, gender empowerment, sustainable production, and inclusive economic growth, the study underscores the commission's significance as a transformative institution. KVIC's alignment with the principles of sustainable development offers a powerful model for promoting inclusive growth and addressing the contemporary challenges of poverty, inequality, and environmental degradation. Through this examination, the paper seeks to highlight KVIC's enduring relevance in shaping India's path toward a more equitable, sustainable, and self-reliant future.

Objectives of KVIC

1. To cultivate a thriving and self-sustaining rural community.
2. To generate employment opportunities, promoting economic growth in rural areas.
3. To improve the market competitiveness and commercial viability of KVI products.
4. To empower economically disadvantaged groups by fostering self-reliance and financial independence.

Functions of KVIC

- Ensure a steady supply of raw materials and tools for uninterrupted production.
- Develop shared facilities for efficient processing and marketing.
- Implement strategies to boost sales and expand market reach.
- Promote research and innovation in production techniques and equipment.
- Provide financial support to strengthen Khadi and Village Industries.
- Establish and enforce quality standards to maintain product authenticity and industry reputation

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Smita Buragohain (2017) investigates the contribution of KVI to the promotion of micro-enterprises in Dibrugarh District. KVI has played a crucial role in fostering employment opportunities in rural areas, requiring minimal capital investment. The study examines the KVI sector's performance, focusing on production, employment, and sales, alongside an analysis of KVI units' production behaviour. The findings reveal that KVI units exhibit increasing returns to scale. The paper provides a detailed assessment of the sector's impact on rural industrial development, highlighting its role in supporting micro-enterprises and fostering economic growth.

Dr. Kh. Dhiren Meitei and O. Deepakkumar Singh. (2013) analyses the socio-economic profile of KVI artisans in Manipur, highlighting the significance of rural industries as a livelihood source. It explores the potential of various KVI sectors and assesses artisans' awareness of funding opportunities for establishing rural industries, contributing to the region's economic development.

Shazia Hussain, Aijaz Abdullah and Fayaz Ahamd (2021) examines the performance of KVI in Jammu and Kashmir under the PMEGP. While significant progress was made in terms of cases sanctioned, funds released, and production, employment generation did not meet expectations. The negative impact of political conflicts and the 2014-2015 floods on the region's economy was a key factor. The study concludes that KVIB plays a vital role in combating unemployment and reducing rural-urban migration, with recommendations for enhancing performance through improved financial, technical, and marketing support.

Murugan K Kethayagounder (2021) examines the significance of KVI in India's rural development, emphasizing their role in employment generation, economic self-reliance, and community building. Despite challenges from globalization, KVI has shown resilience through growth in production, sales, and employment. However, issues such as dependency on government funding, lack of innovation, and weak branding persist. The paper underscores the critical need to strengthen KVI to address rural unemployment and sustain India's cultural and economic heritage.

Smt. S. D. Khanapuri And Dr. S. G. Kulkarni (2018) – This study explores the role of KVI in Belagavi District, highlighting their importance in India's rural economy. KVI units, with high labour-to-capital ratios and low investment requirements, are key to job creation, poverty reduction, and economic growth. By utilizing local resources and unskilled labour, KVI fosters entrepreneurship and strengthens domestic markets, making them essential for sustainable rural development.

Anil Kumar Mohanty and Dr. Anup Kumar Roy (2023) – this study examine employment trends in India, highlighting post-reform improvements in employment generation despite setbacks from the COVID-19 pandemic. They stress the need for balanced growth between rural and urban sectors to address imbalances in labor force and employment rates. The study calls for strategic investments to sustain growth and achieve long-term economic stability, aligning with India's vision for sustainable development by its 75th anniversary.

Anandi Pyne (2017) – This paper explores the role of globalization, liberalization, and privatization in shaping the global economy, with a focus on the significant contribution of MSMEs to national GDP, employment, and exports. It highlights the importance of Khadi in India, both as a livelihood source and a means of preserving traditional skills. The study assesses the performance of the Khadi sector, identifying its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges, and suggests strategies to overcome these challenges in the evolving market.

Dr. B. Shailaja (2022) – The research highlights the significant role of MSMEs in fostering economic growth, reducing regional disparities, and promoting equitable income distribution.

Within this sector, the KVI play a pivotal role by generating employment, enhancing exports, and driving rural development. The research focuses on the efforts of the KVIC to boost production, sales, and employment in rural areas, emphasizing the comparative performance of KVI. It also examines the interrelationship and functional dynamics among key performance variables.

Ms. Priyanka Raghani And Dr. Jigna Trivedi (2021) – The research investigates the challenges faced by Khadi marketers, particularly those managing KhadiBhandars, in the promotion and sale of Khadi apparel. Despite its historical significance and role in supporting the rural economy, the acceptance of Khadi remains low. The analysis identifies the key barriers to its widespread adoption and highlights the issues in its marketing. Recommendations to enhance Khadi's appeal include leveraging celebrity endorsements, expanding online sales, promoting exports, and investing in quality improvement research. These measures aim to establish Khadi as a sustainable and enduring fabric, reinforcing its cultural importance in India.9

Dr. Karamjeet Singh and M. Saeed (2011) – This paper explores the role of rural entrepreneurship, focusing on KVI in India. It highlights the importance of rural industries in addressing unemployment, environmental issues, and the concentration of industries in urban areas. Despite government efforts to support these industries, challenges such as infrastructural limitations, outdated technology, and lack of financial support hinder their growth. The paper stresses the urgent need to modernize rural industries to ensure their survival and continued contribution to the economy.

P. Sudhakar ,Nalla Bala Kalyan Kumar and A. Padmavathi (2012) – This paper analyses employment trends in India from 1998 to 2010, focusing on the organized sector, which includes both public and private sectors. Despite population growth, employment growth has not kept pace, leading to a rising unemployment rate. The study examines male and female employment trends, as well as sector-wise employment patterns. The findings challenge common perceptions and highlight the need for a transformative approach to employment in India to address its socio-economic challenges.

Reetu Murlidhar Tanwani, Dr. Mahendra. H. Maisuria (2020) – This paper evaluates the performance of KVI within India's MSME sector, focusing on its contributions to employment, rural development, and exports. It highlights the role of the KVIC in fostering sector growth through various initiatives. Despite its successes, the paper identifies challenges that KVIC faces, stressing the need for solutions to ensure sustainable growth and further development of KVI.

RESEARCH GAP

This paper differentiates itself from existing body of literature by employing a quantitative approach of the relationship between production and employment in the Khadi and Village Industries (KVI) sector. And unlike previous studies that primarily focus on the qualitative aspects of KVI's impact on rural employment, poverty alleviation, and cultural preservation, this research utilizes correlation, regression, and ANOVA to establish a strong, positive correlation between increased production and job creation. The analysis highlights KVI's potential as a key driver of economic sustainability, demonstrating how growth in production directly contributes to rural economic development and social equity. Additionally, the study links KVI's growth to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly emphasizing employment generation and rural empowerment. By quantifying the economic impact of production growth, this paper positions KVI not only as a cultural and heritage-based initiative but also as a sustainable model that can significantly contribute to India's long-term socio-economic stability.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study examines the impact of KVI sector on employment generation, economic sustainability, and social development in India. It analyses the relationship between production and employment within the KVI sector, emphasizing its crucial role in fostering rural employment, alleviating poverty, and driving sustainable economic growth. The findings highlight the significance of the KVI in advancing national socio-economic objectives, particularly in line with the UNs Sustainable Development Goals. Additionally, the study provides a comprehensive statistical framework that illustrates the strong connection between production growth and employment, offering valuable insights for future policy decisions aimed at enhancing the sector's contribution to India's rural economy. Overall, this research enriches the ongoing discourse on rural development, economic self-reliance, and sustainable livelihoods

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the role of Khadi and Village Industries in generating employment opportunities
2. To evaluate the impact of Khadi and Village Industries on economic sustainability
3. To explore the contribution of Khadi and Village Industries towards achieving social development.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

(H₀₁): There is no significant impact of production on employment generation in the Khadi and Village Industries sector.

(H₁₁): There is a significant impact of production on employment generation in the Khadi and Village Industries sector.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

A quantitative methodology is employed to examine the effect of production on employment within the Khadi and Village Industries sector over the period from 2016-2017 to 2022-2023. It is based on secondary data obtained from authoritative sources, including the Annual Reports of the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), the Khadi and Village Industries Commission (KVIC), and other relevant government publications. Statistical analysis is conducted using SPSS software, incorporating correlation and regression techniques. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson test and ANOVA are applied to ensure the validity and statistical significance of the model.

OVERVIEW OF KHADI AND VILLAGE INDUSTRIES (KVI) (2016-17 TO 2022-23)

Table 1: KVI Production and Employment (2016-17 To 2022-23)

Year	Production (Rs. in Lakh)	Employment (In Lakh Persons)
2016-17	4263109	136.4
2017-18	4808141	140.36
2018-19	5813034	146.99
2019-20	6766731	152.73
2020-21	7223515	159.06
2021-22	8428993	167.61
2022-23	9595667	177.12

Source – MSMEs Annual Report (2016-17 to 2022-23)

Figure 1: KVI Production and Employment (2016-17 to 2022-23)

Source – MSMEs Annual Report (2016–2017 to 2022–2023)

The data on the production (in Rs. Lakh) and employment (in Lakh persons) within the Khadi sector from 2016-17 to 2022-23. Analyzing this data reveals several key trends and observations.

The production in the Khadi sector shows a consistent upward trajectory over the years. In 2016-17, the production was Rs. 4,263,109 lakh, and by 2022-23, it increased to Rs. 9,595,667 lakh. This signifies a continuous rise in the overall production capacity and output of the sector. The production figures are characterized by steady year-on-year increases, with the largest increase occurring between 2021-22 and 2022-23. The growth in Khadi and Village Industries (KVI) production can be primarily attributed to the increasing consumer demand for environmentally conscious and sustainable goods, along with government initiatives that have positioned Khadi as a symbol of self-reliance and national pride.

Employment in the sector also follows a similar upward trend. Starting from 136.4 lakh persons in 2016-17, the number of individuals employed in the Khadi sector rose to 177.12 lakh persons by 2022-23. This increase in employment aligns with the sector’s expanding production, indicating that as production levels grow, the sector is generating more job opportunities. The increase in employment is consistent, with a particularly notable rise in the number of employed persons between 2021-22 and 2022-23.

The data demonstrates not only growth in production but also a corresponding increase in employment, with the sector playing a central role in providing sustainable livelihoods. By integrating traditional practices with modern economic frameworks, the sector contributes significantly to economic sustainability and social development. The rise in both production and employment is indicative of the sector’s potential to continue driving inclusive growth, fostering social equity, and contributing to environmental sustainability in the years to come.

Table 2: Correlation Result between Production and Employment Generation

Correlations			
		Production (Rs. in Lakh)	Employment (In Lakh Persons)
Production (Rs. in Lakh)	Pearson Correlation	1	.997**
	Sig. (2-Tailed)		.000
	N	7	7
Employment (In Lakh Persons)	Pearson Correlation	.997**	1
	Sig. (2-Tailed)	.000	
	N	7	7

** . Correlation Is Significant at the 0.01 Level (2-Tailed).

Sources: SPSS output

Table 3: Regression Model Summary For Employment And Production (Rs In Lakh)

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error Of The Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.997 ^a	.995	.994	1.13644	1.922

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Production (Rs. in Lakh)
- b. Dependent Variable: Employment (In Lakh Persons)

Table 4: Analysis Of Variance For Employment And Production

ANOVA						
	Model	Sum Of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1284.739	1	1284.739	994.760	.000 ^b
	Residual	6.458	5	1.292		
	Total	1291.197	6			

- a. Dependent Variable: Employment (In Lakh Persons)
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Production (Rs. in Lakh)

Table 5: Coefficients

Coefficients						
	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	103.075	1.681		61.328	.000
	Production (Rs. In Lakh)	0.000008	.000	.997	31.540	.000

Dependent Variable: Employment (In Lakh Persons)

Table 6: Statistical Summary of Residuals

Residuals Statistics					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	135.6847	176.4749	154.3243	14.63295	7
Residual	-2.10561	.73032	.00000	1.03743	7
Std. Predicted Value	-1.274	1.514	.000	1.000	7
Std. Residual	-1.853	.643	.000	.913	7

- a. Dependent Variable: Employment (In Lakh Persons)

INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE EMPLOYMENT GENERATION AND PRODUCTION IN KVI SECTOR

The findings of the statistical analysis offer a thorough insight into the impact of production (in Rs. Lakh) on employment generation (in Lakh persons) within the Khadi and Village Industries (KVI) sector. The correlation analysis presented in Table 2 underscores a remarkably strong positive association between production (measured in Rs. Lakh) and employment generation (measured in Lakh persons) in the KVI sector. The obtained correlation coefficient of 0.997, and coupled with a highly significant p-value of 0.000, the findings indicate that increases in production are closely and proportionally linked to rises in employment. This highlights the inherently labour-intensive nature of the KVI sector, where production growth serves as a critical driver of employment generation. The statistical reliability of these results further emphasizes the pivotal role of production expansion in fostering employment within this sector. Table 3 further strengthens this assertion by presenting the regression model summary, which highlights the model's ability to effectively capture the relationship between production and employment. With an R-squared value of 0.995, the model explains 99.5% of the variation in employment, showcasing a highly

accurate fit. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.994 indicates minimal loss in explanatory power, reinforcing the model's reliability. Moreover, the low standard error of 1.13644 further attests to the precision of the predictions. A Durbin- Watson statistic of 1.922 suggests the absence of significant autocorrelation in the residuals, thereby affirming the independence of the variables and reinforcing the model's reliability.

In Table 4, the ANOVA results assess the overall importance of the regression model. The regression sum of squares, amounting to 1284.739, represents the variation in employment explained by the model. The F-statistic of 994.760, and p-value (significance F) of 0.000, validates the model's statistical significance at the 0.01 level, reinforcing the conclusion that the relationship between production and employment is not due to chance.

Additionally, the residual sum of squares of 6.458 highlights that only a small fraction of the variation in employment remains unexplained, further validating the model's precision and strong predictive capability.

Table 5 outlines the regression coefficients, which quantify the influence of production on employment. The unstandardized coefficient for production, at 0.000008, suggests that an increase of one lakh in production results in a corresponding rise of 0.000008 lakh persons in employment. The statistical significance of this coefficient is confirmed by a t-value of 31.540 and a p-value of 0.000, reinforcing the importance of production as a predictor of employment in the KVI sector. Additionally, the standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.997 highlights the near-perfect correlation between production and employment, emphasizing the strength of their relationship.

Finally, Table 6 presents the residual statistics, providing additional insights into the model's predictive accuracy. The predicted employment values range from 135.6847 lakh to 176.4749 lakh, with a mean of 154.3243 lakh and a standard deviation of 14.63295, indicating a minimal degree of variation around the predicted values. The residuals, representing the discrepancies between the observed and predicted values, have a mean of 0.00000 and a standard deviation of 1.03743, reflecting a close alignment between the two sets of values. The absence of significant residual outliers or extreme values further supports the assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity, reinforcing the model's reliability and robustness in capturing the underlying relationship.

The analysis accepts the alternative hypothesis, confirming that increased production in the Khadi and Village Industries sector significantly impacts employment generation.

Overall, the analysis firmly demonstrates a strong relationship between production and employment in the KVI sector. The regression model, featuring high R-squared values, significant coefficients, and minimal residual variance, effectively illustrates that increased production within the sector directly leads to greater employment. These findings highlight the essential role of increasing production in creating employment opportunities, which in turn contributes to the socio-economic development of rural regions. This growth not only promotes local employment but also supports the overarching goals of economic sustainability and social equity, ensuring that the benefits of development are distributed more evenly across society.

THE ROLE OF KVI IN EMPLOYMENT PROMOTION, SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT, AND ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

The Khadi and village industries sector plays a crucial role in advancing social development, generating employment, and fostering economic sustainability, making it an integral component of rural transformation. By empowering marginalized communities, including

women and artisans, KVI drives social equity through skill development and income generation, while simultaneously preserving cultural heritage and promoting self-reliance. This sector, being highly labour-intensive, significantly contributes to employment generation, particularly in rural areas, offering livelihoods to a large segment of the population and mitigating rural unemployment. As production in the KVI sector grows, there is a corresponding rise in job creation, further establishing the direct relationship between economic output and employment opportunities. Economically, KVI promotes sustainability by encouraging local production, reducing migration to urban centres, and boosting rural incomes. Its focus on environmentally sustainable, renewable products is in alignment with global sustainability objectives, ensuring enduring growth while minimizing environmental impact. Moreover, the KVI sector is essential for the promotion of several United Nations (UNs) Sustainable Development Goals. Goal one, which aims to eliminate poverty, Goal eight, which focuses on promoting decent work and economic growth, and Goal twelve, which advocates for responsible consumption and production, collectively underscore the sector's significant contribution to poverty alleviation, employment generation, and sustainable production practices. These goals are reinforced by the sector's focus on job creation, rural development, and environmentally conscious practices. In essence, the KVI sector not only drives economic development but also contributes to social equity, poverty alleviation, and environmental sustainability, thereby emerging as a cornerstone of inclusive and sustainable growth in India.

CONCLUSION

This study underscores the pivotal role of the Khadi and Village Industries (KVI) sector in advancing India's socio-economic and sustainable development. Through rigorous empirical analysis spanning 2016-17 to 2022-23, the research establishes a robust and statistically significant correlation between production and employment within the KVI sector, and with a correlation coefficient of 0.997 and an R-squared value of 0.995. These findings confirm that increased production directly drives employment growth, highlighting the sector's labour-intensive nature and its critical contribution to job creation, particularly in rural areas.

Beyond its economic impact, the KVI sector is a vehicle for social empowerment, offering marginalized communities, including women and artisans, opportunities for skill development and income generation. This not only promotes social equity but also preserves cultural heritage. Furthermore, the sector's alignment with sustainable practices and its role in producing eco-friendly goods supports environmental conservation, contributing to global sustainability goals. The Khadi and Village Industries (KVI) sector supports UN SDGs by reducing poverty, creating sustainable jobs, and promoting eco-friendly production, KVI makes a substantial contribution to these global objectives. Additionally, it acts as a driving force for inclusive economic development, ensuring ethical and sustainable production while aligning with the broader vision of equitable and environmentally conscious progress.

In conclusion, the KVI sector serves as a critical engine for inclusive economic growth, social development, and environmental sustainability, making it an indispensable component of India's vision for a self-reliant and equitable future. Its continued support and expansion are essential for fostering a sustainable and inclusive development trajectory, where rural communities thrive as active contributors to both national and global progress.

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